

“Vigo en inglés”, a neoliberal urban language policy

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Draft paper

Introduction

This paper deals with an example of neoliberal language policy: the immersion program in English language launched by the municipal authorities of Vigo, Galicia's largest city in Northwest of Spain with 300.000 inhabitants. Every year, this program, called *Vigo en inglés*, establishes a different number of vacancies for students aged 15 which allow them to enjoy a three-week stay in the United Kingdom or the Republic of Ireland. The purpose of this paper is to offer a first reading of this program, based on the specific bases that regulate the 2017 call, as well as an ongoing analysis of in-depth interviews that I have conducted with students who participated in previous editions of the program.

Vigo en inglés: a brief contextualization

Since 2008, *Vigo en inglés* (initially called *Vigo abroad*) has had ten editions, two of them in 2016 (it was not held in 2013 due to political disagreements). So far, the municipal budget allocated to this program exceeds 7 million euros and 4,000 students both from public and private schools have already benefited from it. Depending on the family income, the program may cover all the expenses. For those participants required to pay, the amount varies between 10% and 30% of the total cost, which has been estimated to be 2,400 euros per participant. As of 2014, the Company responsible for its management, organization and development is Newlink Education S.L.

In the last call (March-2017), 657 vacancies were offered with a total budget of 1.700.000 euros. In order to assess the impact of this initiative, we must take into account that there are 2,500 registered 15-year-olds in the city; this implies that around 25% of the target population benefits year after year from this language

policy. In addition, given that the demand is higher than the supply, the rules of the call state some (discriminatory) conditions for accessing the program: i.e. having passed all the subjects at school and having an average grade equal or higher than 7 (out of 10) in English Language in the previous course.

This high demand shows that we find ourselves before a very successful policy by the local government, with a clear social recognition. This implies to admit that the ideologies, discourses and practices of many 'ordinary people' are inoculated by the neoliberal daydream. Contemporary society could not be explained if this were not true.

According to the rules of the last call (BOPP 17/03/2017), the official aim of the program is "to improve English language proficiency and training by encouraging its learning and contact with other cultures in an international environment". In the words of the Mayor of the city, the purpose of the program is to contribute to "the children of Vigo having a fluent competence in English" (Abel Caballero, Mayor of Vigo, July 16th 2008). In practice, the program contributes very moderately to this goal and, to a greater extent, consists of financing a three-week vacation for the adolescent population of the city. That is, on paper we are before a language policy based on a neoliberal reason; in practice, it results into a hidden tourism policy, built out of the banalization of what would be a neoliberal language policy favorable to English. This double fallacy is an eloquent manipulation, with two main subjects: that of the families, who do not have to know they are being deceived and that of the municipal government, which is aware that it is being misleading, but acts as if it isn't. Indeed, it is very different 'not to know' than 'to know' *and* to say that 'one does not know'. In Žižek's words (1989: 25), this is an example of cynicism as a form of functioning of the dominant ideology: "they know very well what they are doing, but still, they are doing it". And all this comes with a significant economic cost.

In addition, as in many linguistic minority contexts (McEwan-Fujita 2005), this type of language policy damages minority languages. Note that Vigo is an officially bilingual city (with two languages, Galician and Spanish), although functionally the Galician language is clearly in a disadvantageous situation. Actually, it would not be an exaggeration to conclude that Vigo is a very castilianized city (González Pascual & Ramallo 2015). Although bilingualism is consolidated *de jure*, Spanish is *de facto* the predominant language in most informal communicative interactions. Overall, Galician is in a clear regressive sociolinguistic situation, with little social dynamism, especially among the youth.

Regarding age, Table 1 shows a downslide in Galician-speaking generations and the option, increasingly common, to use only Castilian. Half of those under the age of 50 speak only Castilian, reaching 76% in the youngest population. The exclusive use of Galician in these age groups is residual, although this is a population group with a good formal command of the language, as a result of their learning in the education system. Even among the older population, many of them with Galician as their first language, the exclusive use of Galician does not reach 20%.

Table 1. Language use in Vigo by age from 2003 to 2013 (in percentage)

	Only Galician		Only Castilian		Galician and Castilian	
	2003	2013	2003	2013	2003	2013
5-14 years	5	1	55	76	40	24
15-29 years	8	2	42	59	50	40
30-49 years	12	5	37	53	51	42
50-64 years	22	8	27	48	51	43
Over 65 years	30	18	33	35	37	47
TOTAL	15	8	38	50	47	42

Source: González Pascual & Ramallo (2015)

In this context, the municipal support for the maintenance of the Galician language in the city is very far from the annual expenditure for promoting the use of English with the *Vigo en inglés* immersion program.

Neoliberalism, language commodification and public policies

My approach fits into a tradition that understands neoliberalism beyond a political economy. In particular, I understand neoliberalism not only as the extension of mercantilist logics to all the spheres of human life, but especially, as a reason which has been thought-out and executed to produce and intervene in subjectivities through the stabilization of dominant forms of thought and social practices with the aim of normalizing submission (see, among many others, Laval & Dardot 2013). It is, in short, a form of psychologization. This tradition is associated with the work of the last Foucault and takes as its starting point the consideration of governmentality as the reason of State. That is, the form of molar and molecular power characteristic of liberalism and neoliberalism.

In that tradition, *Vigo en inglés* could be understood as an example of language commodification (Heller 2010), with no other purpose than to obey the 'orders' of a neoliberal reason designed to promote the strengthening of **human capital**, as the only way the entrepreneur subject has to triumph; that being the subject-entrepreneur of him/herself. It is the return to *Homo oeconomicus*, in the words of Foucault (2007: 264). It enhances the value of language as a commodity that, supposedly, favors efficient work. This appropriation of the forms of communication and relation by capital implies a last step of biopolitics. Through the exploitation and the appropriation of the communicative capacity such as immaterial labor force, biopolitics means the total subsumption of the life of the subject (Fumagalli 2010: 27). Therefore, the commodification of languages involves thinking about them according to what Rossi-Landi (1970: 258) calls "variable linguistic capital"; that is, "the value of the linguistic labor-power expended by men who speak and understand a given language."

Taking all of this into account, the language policy promoted by *Vigo en inglés* (such as knowledge, practice and technology) can be summarized in the following keywords (Canagarajah 2017: 11):

- **Flexibilization.** The language policy adapts to the changing market conditions. In this logic, promoting the use of English as the global language implies greater ease of adaptation by the subject to that flexibility.
- **Tertiarization.** In a communication economy, we move from the 'labor force' to the 'word force', with more and more 'language workers'. All language teaching, particularly English, is oriented from this perspective and, to a lesser extent, towards being the facilitator of intercultural contact.
- **Distinction.** English seems to mobilize added value in the market that justifies the entire economic and political effort. Its "symbolic cachet" is the guarantee of this type of policies.
- **Entrepreneurialism.** Entrepreneurship is a demand of neoliberalism, both at the cost of the subject and institutions. The final beneficiary is the capitalist. The incorporation of English into the linguistic repertoire is a requirement of the neoliberal subject.
- **Human capital.** The ultimate goal of the neoliberal subject is to transform himself into a producer of human capital through gaining aptitudes and predispositions that can be commodified, such as: creativity, adaptability, teamwork, collaboration, tolerance, intercultural understanding, cosmopolitan values, etc.

Perhaps the most determinant objective (and achievement) of neoliberalism has to do with its ability to intervene in the subject's **competences**. Such intervention is designed with the eloquent purpose of transforming the subject into their own manager. Actually, this subject is devised on the basis of supposedly universal values such as human capital, effort and entrepreneurship (Estupiñán Serrano 2016: 18). Therefore, we are dealing with a subject that acts as a counterbalance—freer in appearance and autonomous—to the subject supposedly socialized from

interventionist logics, whereas in practice this neoliberal subject is more resilient, dependent and degraded (Chandler & Reid 2016).

Thus, *Vigo en inglés* is a political technology aimed at strengthening the subject's competence in the market, according to the reasons of that market, but promoted from a public institution. In other words, the municipality of Vigo, far from "controlling" the market, stands as "the voluntary co-producer of norms of competitiveness" (Laval & Dardot 2013: 20). Not only the public authorities do not counteract the business order, but this same order has change public institutions through their commodification. In other words, neoliberal society has internalized that it is no longer necessary to limit the policies of public institutions to guarantee economic freedom. Although capitalism, like any other social formation, has always produced the public institutions, in the neoliberal era this is even more evident (García López 2016). At this point Foucault (2008: 131) situates the "problem of neo-liberalism", that being, "how the overall exercise of political power can be modeled on the principles of a market economy."

From vocation to vacation through ideology

Vigo en inglés is an example of the euphoria / frenzy in which much of the Spanish society (see also Relaño Pastor 2015) —especially, the State, regional or local authorities, but also the families—, positions itself with respect to the importance of English at the current historical moment. This attitude is not, of course, exclusive to the Spanish context. Just as in other latitudes (see for example Park 2009; Piller & Cho 2013), the myth of English is elaborated from a calculated abstraction whose ultimate aim is to strengthen and naturalize —through an exercise of objectification—, a "social norm" that, from a neoliberal reason, is not subject to discussion. That means, it is hardly contested that English is an indispensable language in today's world, a "pure potential" according to Park (2016). It is assumed that we cannot survive without English. In fact, for most people, particularly among young people, "without English, you are dead" (Warriner 2016; Shi & Lin 2016). In

the words of (Majhanovich 2013: 84) "policy makers and parents are convinced that their children will never be able to participate and succeed in the global economy unless they have mastered the English language."

Now, this euphoria is based on a fiction, perhaps on a desire, but very far from the promises that the signifier mobilizes. The euphoric subject is interpellated by a Master-signifier ('English language') which is able to condition, and even determine, much of his/her actions, but not the subjective concrete form through the subject relates him/herself to that Master-signifier (his/her attitudes, ideologies and so on). In part, the "pitfalls of the promise of English" (Park 2011: 444) are innocuous because it is a matter of faith, which often guides even frustration.

Of course, I realize that learning English in the neoliberal context could mobilizes returns. However, one thing is recognizing this effect, and naturalizing and universalizing it is another, turning it into a *telos*, but ignoring that this *telos* has a great dependence on the structures, relationships and limitations that characterize the functioning of each field of the market. In general, I consider that English, understood as a commodification with exchange value, is useless and unnecessary, even in a scenario in which the market demands it. Actually, such a demand, on many occasions, functions in the abstract—as a Master-signifier to which we have referred—and creates a relation of dependence on the subject with respect to that signifier.

In contrast with this view, the language ideologies articulated around English as capital are undeniable. This is the language ideology that underlines the *Vigo en inglés* program. It repeats many of the topics that serve to reproduce a neoliberal ideology that holds that, without capitalization in foreign languages, the chances of personal and professional success are reduced:

The knowledge of a language other than one's own contributes in an essential way to the integral training of the students, and its learning

has become a key objective of educational systems, both because it favors the free movement and the communication, as per the requirements of the labor market (taken from 2017 call).

This mantra has allowed a language commodification, which can only be understood as a fantasy of "human needs", as it is with all the commodities in capitalism ("the fetishism of commodities", according Marx). In the words of Tomšič (2015: 28-29, our emphasis):

Even if commodities are not produced with the aim of satisfying human needs but first and foremost to support exchange and stimulate consumption, one of the cornerstones of production of value, *they have to maintain the fiction of usefulness and need*, no matter how abstract, futile and fantasmatic. It is precisely the fantasy that supports the union of use-value and exchange-value, matter without qualities and qualities without matter, two heterogeneous and unrelated levels.

In addition to the above, a final characterization of the *Vigo en inglés* program is necessary. As I stated before, the proposal itself is an example of a false language policy: in other words, we are dealing with an effective 'holiday program' that has nothing to do with the supposed benefits of a well-designed and efficient language immersion program. Of course, as we have already said, this program has been mainly applauded and demanded by the citizenship, in particular by the beneficiaries, including their families. Thus, all our informants have shown their satisfaction with the experience. Now, one thing is enjoying three weeks of (semi)holidays in the United Kingdom or Ireland, among friends (groups of 25) and away from home regime and/or parental control—with all the usual significance this has in the eyes of a teenager subject—and a very different thing is attributing this satisfaction to the improvement of the proficiency and practice of English by the students.

According to our informants, the exposure to the English language is not total. In fact, a good part of their daily routine is developed along the rest of the group coming from Vigo. English is used with the host families and at the schools, as well as in some extracurricular activities. However, these latter activities are developed with the peer group, i.e. the language of interaction is the language of each student, dominating Spanish.

End

Policies supporting English language as an 'objective' value are one motto of global society. Because of all its implications pervading all the levels of society it is an ideology that requires analysis and a response from a (new) perspective that allows a better understanding. According to Block (2017), now is the moment for a new turn of the socially applied linguistics, one that places political economy and, particularly, the neoliberalization of language at the center of the analysis (Shin & Park 2016). This is the perspective from which I have tried to approach the language immersion program called *Vigo en inglés*.

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